

Determinants of Catastrophic Health Expenditure among Rural Households in Northeast India

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Abstract: In India, healthcare financing is heavily reliant on out-of-pocket expenditure, particularly among the poor and vulnerable. Public health insurance schemes such as Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY) use Socio-Economic Caste Census (SECC) deprivation criteria to identify eligible households. The study attempts to identify socio-economic determinants of catastrophic health expenditure. The study uses unit-level data from the NSS 75th Round (2017-18), restricted to rural households in Northeast India. By rebuilding four deprivation indicators (D2, D3, D5, and D7) from similar NSS variables, SECC-2011 eligibility is proxied. SECC-eligible households were those that met at least one deprivation requirement. After adjusting for sociodemographic factors, survey-weighted logistic regression was used to investigate the relationship between SECC eligibility and health insurance coverage. There is a significant eligibility-coverage disparity: 61.7% of rural households were qualified for SECC, only 11.7% had insurance, and roughly 88% did not. Enrolment is not guaranteed by SECC-based eligibility, which emphasizes the need to improve enrolment processes beyond eligibility requirements.

Keywords: Public Health insurance, SECC eligibility, Uninsured households, Rural India, Northeast.

1. Introduction:

In India, healthcare financing is so high that it continues to pose a substantial burden on households, with Out-of-pocket (OOP) expenses accounting for a major share of total health spending (Deol, 2022). To address these challenges, the government has initiated various health insurance schemes, one of which is the Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY), aimed at improving access to healthcare and providing financial risk protection for citizens. These initiatives, to some extent, reduce households' out-of-pocket expenditure. National Health Account data for 2021-22 show that Out-of-Pocket Expenditure (OOPE) in healthcare is decreasing, largely due to increased government expenditure and the expansion of government-funded schemes (Press Information Bureau, 2024). According to the Economic Survey 2024-25, out-of-pocket expenditure as a share of total healthcare expenditure declined from 62.6% in 2020-21 to 39.4% in 2014-15, alongside increased government health spending and expanded social security and insurance coverage, reflecting progress in financial protection (Koul S, 2024). However, despite the expansion of public insurance coverage, many eligible households remain uninsured.

A household is considered to face catastrophic health expenditure when out-of-pocket healthcare expenditure exceeds a specified proportion of household consumption expenditure.

The study may use the WHO-recommended threshold approach.

A household will be classified as suffering from CHE if:

- healthcare expenditure exceeds 10% of total household expenditure, or
- 25% of non-food expenditure.

The analysis of national representative data from the NSS 75th Round aims to close these gaps. It also considers the economic and behavioural factors affecting households without insurance. The purpose of the study is to determine the key

factors and economic factors that contribute to rural households in Northeast India lacking public health insurance.

1.1 Conceptual Framework

For eligible households under public health insurance schemes such as Ayushman Bharat - PM-JAY, the study relies on the Socio-Economic Caste Census (SECC) 2011. The SECC 2011 defines the eligibility criteria for Rural and Urban areas (Harish et al.). Seven deprivation criteria determine whether households are eligible for public health insurance. If any household meets any requirements, it is considered eligible for PM-JAY [Table 1].

Table 1
SECC Deprivation Criteria (Rural Area)

Deprivation Code	Description
D1	Only one room with Kucha walls and Kucha roof
D2	No adult member between the ages of 16 and 59
D3	Female-headed household with no adult male member between 16 and 59
D4	Disabled member and no able-bodied adult member
D5	SC/ST households
D6	No literate adult above 25 years
D7	Landless households deriving major income from manual casual labour

For Urban Areas, SECC eligibility is defined by the occupation of the household, such as rag picker, Beggar, Domestic worker, Street vendor, construction worker, etc. (Socio-Economic and Caste Census). Any household that meets these criteria is automatically included in the SECC eligibility category.

Methodology

The study used secondary data from the NSS 75th Round (2017-18). The survey, titled 'Household Social Consumption on Health', provides detailed information on the health status, hospitalisation expenditure, and health insurance coverage of households in Northeast India (Drèze and Khera).

For this Study, we have reconstructed all these deprivation indicators, i.e., D2, D3, D5 & D7, within the NSS dataset by considering the relevant variables. The SECC framework identifies deprivation among rural households based on several socio-demographic conditions (D1–D7). Among these, four indicators—D2, D3, D5, and D7—were considered in this study as they directly reflect economic vulnerability and social deprivation relevant to public health insurance eligibility. Since the SECC and NSS surveys differ in design and purpose, the original SECC

indicators were proxied and reconstructed using conceptually equivalent variables available in the NSS dataset.

Later, we will construct the SECC-eligible variable by aggregating these deprivation indicators. A household was then classified as SECC-eligible (value = 1) if it satisfied at least one of the four deprivation criteria, and non-eligible (value = 0) otherwise.

$$\text{Formally, SECC Eligible} = \begin{cases} \text{if any D2, D3, D5, D7} = 1 \\ 0 \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This reconstructed SECC eligibility variable serves as a proxy for identifying poor and vulnerable households within the NSS dataset, aligning with the targeting approach of public health insurance schemes such as Ayushman Bharat – Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY). The study uses household-level data and a cross-sectional analytical design. The home serves as the analytical unit. The analysis's major goal is to pinpoint the economic and behavioural factors that contribute to households in India not being covered by any public health insurance program.

Study Design

The current study is based on the rural sector of Northeast India. The analysis relies on SECC-2011 deprivation indicators to define eligibility for public health insurance. We use unit-level data from the NSS 75th Round (2017–18) for rural Northeast India. SECC-2011 eligibility is proxied by reconstructing available deprivation indicators from the NSS: D2, D3, D5 & D7. A household is classified as SECC-eligible if it meets at least one of these criteria.

Results

Table 2 gives an overview of the number of insured and uninsured households among the households in Northeast India, which shows that the majority of the households are uninsured, i.e. 88.3% whereas only 11.7% households have some private or public health insurance.

Table 2: Percentage of insured vs. uninsured households

Insurance Status	Percentage
Insured households	11.70
Uninsured households	88.30

Source: Authors' calculation from 75th Round Data

Table 3 shows the number of eligible and ineligible households for public health insurance in India. It shows that 61.71% of households in the Northeastern region of India are eligible for health insurance, whereas 38.29% are ineligible.

Table 3: Percentage of eligible vs. non-eligible households

Insurance Status	Percentage
Non-eligible households	38.29
Eligible households	61.71

Source: Authors' calculation from 75th Round Data

Table 4 depicts the eligibility gap of between the insured and uninsured households in Northeast India. Among SECC-eligible households, 87% remain uninsured, indicating a significant coverage gap despite eligibility.

Table 4: Uninsured Households

Variable	Observation	Mean	Standard Dev.
Uninsured	490,380	.883	.341

Source: Authors' calculation from 75th Round Data

Discussion

The results show that most households are uninsured (88.3%), while 61.71% are eligible for public health insurance schemes. It highlights a large exclusion gap in India's public health insurance system. Even though most of the households qualify for PFHI schemes, actual enrolment remains exceptionally low. A similar study in Mysuru noted that a significant proportion of households had poor awareness, and that utilisation of the public health insurance was also low (Jin et al.). The reason for the eligibility-coverage Gap could be poor awareness, complex enrolment process, administrative errors, limited trust in government schemes, lack of network hospitals, etc. National representative data found that only about 40% of households have any member insured; many eligible households remain uncovered — indicating persistent under-coverage despite the expansion of PFHI schemes (Shruddha et al.). Another study of public insurance schemes found that by 2016, coverage for AB-PMJAY had fallen far short of the original target; many BPL households or eligible families remained excluded (Ambade et al.).

The findings are consistent with existing literature showing that an American Study estimates the share of uninsured Americans who are eligible for public health insurance programs (Dubay, Holahan, and Cook). Another study examined the impact of health insurance programs on children's insurance coverage (Dubay and Kenney). The study develops a new method for reconstructing deprivation-based SECC-eligibility using NSS 75th Round data. Unlike most studies that focus on financial protection or coverage, this work investigates the determinants of non-enrolment among households. The study uses a large, nationally representative dataset covering rural North Eastern India.

The analysis is restricted to rural households because the SECC-2011 deprivation indicators used to determine eligibility (D2, D3, D5, D7) are specifically defined for the rural context. The study's analysis is based on cross-sectional data, which limits the ability to infer causal relationships between SECC deprivation indicators and insurance coverage.

The study reveals a substantial eligibility-coverage gap in insurance schemes. This is because the system relies on passive enrolment, and most remain uninsured due to poor enrolment systems and low awareness, so stronger direct outreach is required. The study highlights that the eligibility structure can reach certain vulnerable groups. However, some groups of households remain disproportionately unemployed, suggesting the need for assistance-enrolment mechanisms such as door-to-door registration and social work. To minimize the financial burden on uninsured households, the government may implement automatic or default enrolment based on SECC lists. These changes may increase coverage rates and im-

prove access equity. Again, to enhance scheme uptake, insurance enrolment can be linked to existing administrative networks such as the Public Distribution System (PDS), MGNREGA worksites, gram panchayat offices, and ASHA outreach. These "automatic contact points" would allow eligible households to verify their SECC status and complete enrolment during routine welfare interactions, thereby reducing informational and transactional barriers. From society's point of view, closing the eligibility–coverage gap has direct implications for poverty reduction. In rural Northeast India, lack of financial protection during illness leads to catastrophic health spending, distress borrowing, and asset sales, pushing households into a "medical poverty trap." Ensuring SECC households are effectively enrolled would reduce health-induced financial shocks, prevent medical impoverishment, and support inclusive social protection.

Conclusion

The study examined the determinants of uninsured status among rural Indian households using the NSS 75th Round data. The study found an apparent mismatch between eligibility and coverage in public health insurance schemes: although many households meet SECC deprivation criteria, a large share remains uninsured.

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